

IMPROVING PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS AS AN EDITORIAL PROBLEM

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ABSTRSCT: *In the article, as an editorial problem of improving the professional training of future teachers, the method of teaching information and communication technologies of teachers in the higher education system, the issue of organizing a lesson using Web-technologies and thereby forming their qualifications and skills It was said that the study of this problem is one of the urgent issues of insufficient research, in particular, the lack of skills and competences in the use and application of Web-technologies in the course of the lesson.*

KEY WORDS: *Professional training, modern educational process, pedagogical problem, Internet, information, computer and information, future teachers.*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, within the framework of the implementation of the priority national project of education, the improvement of the professional preparation of future teachers for the educational process is being actively carried out. By modernizing the educational process of modern technical means of teaching, distance learning develops the skills of independent learning of future teachers, forms creative abilities, and increases efficiency through the development of a continuous education system.

In modern conditions, the main goal of professional training of future teachers in higher education institutions is to train personnel with independent creative thinking. Only having special knowledge is not enough to prepare a good graduate, it is necessary to take into account the intellectual competence of the person, the level of creative potential [1].

Effective organization of the educational process also includes pedagogical research.

The social point of view of the pedagogue is formed and develops in the form of views, value system already during the general secondary education school. Valuable attitude towards pedagogical activity, in a broad sense, represents the orientation that forms the basis of the teacher's personality.

"Value system" is a set of values that have a stable, constant and dynamic-functional relationship and are formed in the process of professional training on the basis of value-oriented activities.

The system of socially significant values developed in the future teachers reflects the description of the attitude towards the environment and oneself and is manifested in the process of preparation for professional activities, which leads to qualitative changes in the interrelated axiological components of pedagogical training. It was clarified that it is a directed objective process [2].

A number of scientific researches have been conducted on the training of future teachers. For example, Z. Rakhimov studied the didactic features of developing the creativity of future vocational teachers.

Researcher U. Urazova's dissertation on the topic "Improving the technology of preparing the future professional education pedagogue for planning activities" determined the methodological (integrative) basis of improving the content of the future teacher's professional training, the formation of the professional (professional) personality of the future teachers. scientific recommendations have been developed on improving the practical oriented model of professional training, improving the criteria for evaluating the level of development of professional competences of future teachers, improving technologies for developing the levels of professional activity of future teachers [3].

Also, a number of pedagogic scientists of our country include G.Al'dzhanova, Z.Ismailova, N.Mannapova, Sh.Nurullaeva, D.Ro'zieva, M.Kuronov, N.Egamberdieva, M.Urazova, H. Hamzaev studied the pedagogical aspects of training future teachers.

N.A.Muslimov agrees with the opinion about the structure of the future teacher's preparation for professional activity and distinguishes motivational, knowledge-oriented, operational-behavioral, emotional-volitional and evaluation components.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Vocational training is a dynamic phenomenon determined by many internal and external factors. That is why we face many difficulties in determining its essence and indicators. Systematic-structural analysis and functional approach allow to describe professional training through the following stages: 1) adaptation to the profession; 2) self-actualization of the student in his cognitive and professional activities; 3) formation of professional-pedagogical activity in students takes place in the knowledge-activity approach (we equate this stage with professional practice); 4) the formation of personal qualities in the performance of pedagogical research, which involves feeling the need to perform all steps of creative pedagogical activity, creative inspiration [4].

Vocational training is a pedagogical process that implies the goal of rapid acquisition of skills necessary for the performance of a specific job or set of jobs.

In the "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" preparation is defined as follows:

1. Getting ready; preparation, act of preparation; readiness
2. Readiness, state of readiness.

S.S. Salavatova suggests that the concept of "professional training" includes the formation of professional interests, views, imaginations, and behavioral standards corresponding to them.

J.A. Hamidov and others study the specific characteristics of the manifestation of the phenomenon of readiness for pedagogical activity, its essence determined by the functional classification of the teacher's professional activities.

A. Tokhtaev, A. Khamidov studied professional readiness and distinguished the structural and functional criteria of this readiness. Applying this approach to environmental education, Sh.M.Avazov, I.Sh.Ismatov clarified.

As shown by N. Ashurova and others, from the point of view of the future teacher's professional readiness, his knowledge, skills, activity and attitude to educational work are measured at each distinguished level.

In our opinion, according to the analysis of the above scientific researches, the development of professional competence in the process of professional training of future teachers based on Web-technologies is as follows: to know, to achieve the full implementation of their actions; The methodology of developing the professional training of future teachers based on web technologies, comparing and summarizing the level of influence of the general training level and age characteristics on didactic goals, and improving visual information, animated images, Web resources based on intensive adaptation to students with special needs; increase the professional training point of view in the organization of the educational process in higher education institutions; use of opportunities aimed at effective organization of the educational process at the reproductive, investigative or creative level.

The technology of training future teachers, aimed at developing the competence of professional training of future teachers.

Content of development of professional training of future teachers When creating Web-programs, scientists rely on the achievements of applied science.

In our research, among the important components of the organization of the function of the development of professional training of future teachers, importance is given to professional skills - as a tool that ensures effective results of professional activity. This will lighten all the scientific and methodological burdens of future

teachers in developing their professional training.

From another point of view, editor D.I. Yunusova-method of activity considers the acquisition of knowledge about the initial level of skill formation as a skill. Thus, the difference in the definitions of scientists is in the ratio of skills and qualifications, in the assessment of their role in future educational development.

According to T.T. Vezirov, skill is readiness for conscious, specific actions or the ability to consciously achieve a goal in a changing environment.

As one of the components of the educational content, skills are especially important, because if they are taught to acquire knowledge independently, the cognitive activity of future teachers will develop. This can be done only by developing the skills of future teachers. A characteristic feature of this component of higher education is that skills are an operational part of knowledge. Knowledge and skills are closely related to each other and are formed at the same time [4].

Redagogical encyclopedia defines skills as actions acquired by a person, provided by a network of acquired knowledge and skills.

Nowadays, the term "Professional training" is widely used. They should be considered not as independent training, but as certain labor (practical) skills that describe a clearly defined scope and high quality of labor actions, without which the quality and requirements of modern production imposed by modern production It is not possible to provide quantitative requirements.

The types of activities indicated in the state higher education institution certainly do not cover all the types of activities that the student may encounter in his practical work. But, first of all, it is impossible to foresee all types of activity, because practice is more diverse than any systematic. Second, while building basic skills and self-esteem, a person learns at a higher level some types of education in the occupation, then continues education and professional skills and improves.

In the first step of knowledge in professional training, the task of creating an image of the object being studied - a gradually deepening understanding that provides understanding based on a general idea is created [5].

The second step is a deep understanding of the studied material. All mental operations are used here: comparison, generalization, induction, deduction, etc.

The educational material obtained in the process of perception and understanding requires further strengthening and improvement. This training is the special activity of future teachers: repetition, teaching, memorization. At the same time, tasks that contribute to the formation of skills and abilities are used. Tasks of a search and creative nature, which ensure the acquisition of material and the development of knowledge skills of future students, are of particular importance (shown in Figure 1).

1- picture Teaching steps in professional training

The last stage of education is the process of applying knowledge, skills and abilities in practical activities. This process is carried out with a step-by-step and consistent increase in the role of independence of future teachers: from following specific instructions to complete creative independence. At the same time, the teacher supervises the activities of future students and creates conditions for self-monitoring and analysis of successes and failures.

All stages of the educational process are dialectically complex and in conflict, and practically inseparable. Knowledge of individual steps and their interrelationship allows to correctly understand the essence of the educational process [6].

A motivated student can manage the situation independently, know it (including acquiring the necessary new knowledge); correctly defining the goal of actions in accordance with objective conditions determines its reality and achievement; in accordance with the situation, to determine the specific means and methods of implementation of actions, this goal and available opportunities; improvement during activities, their development and finally reaching the goal. Naturally, the specific types of activities of future teachers, including professional activities, involve only a part of the listed components. Thus, the goal, means and methods of the implementation of pure activity are determined externally to a person, respectively, cognitive, value-oriented and roeactional comronents are mainly reduced [7].

Before each practical preparation, a project, a plan - a method of action is built. Building a method of action is a specific cognitive and value-oriented activity: knowledge of the situation, its correlation with existing knowledge; revision, reconstruction of knowledge system; based on the identification of action opportunities and others. The method of action includes ideas about the purpose of action, methods of execution and control according to intermediate and final results.

It is improved by the future learner independently or with the help of the learner's explanation, instruction, demonstration of action. At the initial step of mastering the movement, when the future learner has little experience in performing it, the image is still incomplete and the wrong movement is the starting direction. Professional training is carried out on the basis of knowledge, skills and qualifications. The intermediate and final results of professional training are related to the order of action, on the basis of which the necessary corrections are made to the action..

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that improving the professional training of future teachers has been studied as a pedagogical problem. In the course of this research, scientific-theoretical literature on clarifying pedagogical problems in the process of improving the professional training of future teachers on the basis of Web-technology was analyzed..

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